

Original Research Article

Nurses knowledge and practice regarding GCS techniques implementation

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Abstract

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The Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) is one of the best and common scoring systems used to describe the level of consciousness in a person who had a traumatic brain injury. It was invented in 1974 by Graham Teasdale and Bryan j. jennet. It has 3 major components first is eye-opening, second is verbal response and the third one is the motor response. The best score of GCS is 15/15 and the worst score is 3/15. Across sectional observational study performed on 150 nurses to observe nurse's knowledge and practice regarding GCS techniques implementation. According to this study a lot of participants did not have sufficient knowledge of GCS implementation techniques in ICU and emergency departments. The study revealed that only 34.3% of Nurses have sufficient knowledge about GCS assessment and interpretation, on the other hands 65.7% of the population did not know about GCS assessment and interpretation. It is concluded that the majority of nurses have insufficient knowledge and weak Assessment regarding GCS.

Keywords: Nurses, GCS, Practice, and knowledge

INTRODUCTION

The Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) is one of the best and common scoring systems used to describe the level of consciousness in a person who had a traumatic brain injury. It was invented in 1974 by Graham Teasdale and Bryan j. jennet. The Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) is used to measure the severity of an acute brain injury. The GCS has three components which include eye, verbal, and motor responses. The three values are measured separately and last summed together for observing the final score (Hockenberry and Wilson, 2018). The Glasgow Coma scale assigns numeric values which range from 1 to 5 for each one activity which comprises eye-opening, best motor response, and best verbal response to measure the level of awareness and responsiveness. GCS scale affords the score which ranges 3 to 15. The patients with scores of 3 to 8 are usually said to be in neurological injuries like a coma. The lowest possible

GCS is three which may be deep coma or death, while the highest is 15 which means fully attentive and oriented (Healey et al., 2016). In GCS scale firstly observed the response of eye-opening. The Spontaneous eye-opening indicates that the stimulation mechanisms in the brainstem are active in the patient. This indicates that the patient is conscious and not at the risk of neurological deterioration (Kimboka, 2017). Patients were able to open their eyes without any external stimulus that indicates that arousal mechanisms in the brainstem are intact. In the rare case of the persistent somatic state, the patient has a natural opening without awareness (Mattei and Teasdale, 2019).

The verbal stimulus is included any loud sound that makes the patient open the eyes. The thing is only important is that the sound should be loud adequate to arouse a reaction (Mushtaq et al., 2017). The patient with

serious head injuries is not able to show spontaneous reply to the eye-opening. For that kind of patient, the verbal and physical stimuli needed. This assessment not only recognizes the neural problem but also notices the primary signs of impediments of brain trauma and acute head injuries (Hien, 2017). To assess the severity of neurological damage the painful stimulus is given. The health care provider must be sure that the patient should not give a painful stimulus before a verbal one. The painful stimuli were given at the nail bed with a pen or pinching the trapezius muscle or rubbing the sternum. If the patient giving no response of eye-opening to even painful stimulus that condition might be showing some serious mental problem (Frellesen et al., 2018). Active and meaningful verbal communication is a very important part when it aims to deliver excellent care to the patient in the health care setting. In nursing carrier, operative communication is most significant because it effects on patient recovery process during the assessment (Nisa et al., 2017). The patient with neurological damage also scoring for the ability to convert. If the patient able to involve in conversation that comprises appropriate sentences and words even is not answering appropriately to the question who, where, and what (Reith et al., 2016). During the assessment of the Glasgow coma scale, it must be considered by the health care provider that the facial damage to the speaking areas can cause the patient to compromised speech responses. In this condition, the patient only observed how much he alert (Chou et al., 2017). In scoring to the Glasgow coma incomprehensible speech or having no verbal response indicated the patient severe head injuries and the patient must be assessed for the further procedures (Teasdale and Iverson, 2019). The learning environment is tense for all beginners. Nursing education is especially important in a critical situation when a patient assessment is required in active way and this knowledge practice in nursing education which covers the theoretic and practical practiced characteristic (Ambar et al., 2018).

The motor response of the patient in the Glasgow coma scale becomes very important especially in the patients which not giving a verbal response or at least are at a confusing level in conversation. In motor responses, the patient observed for obeying commands for movements (Chandrasekhar et al., 2017). The painful stimuli are given in a standardized manner and continued for an appropriate time to assess motor response. The places for a painful stimulus have pinched the trapezius, firm rubbing movement, over the sternum, or press over the supraorbital notch (Braine and Cook, 2017). A range of movements is possible in a patient who is not restricting to a painful stimulus. It can vary from a Normal Flexion which is rapid withdrawal. In Abnormal Flexion, there is adduction, for example, internal rotation of the shoulder. Between these two extremes of movements, there may be different patterns and also both types of movements may be seen at the same time in a patient

(Healey et al., 2016). In the assessment of GCS scale, some patient is showing no response to a painful stimulus. The health care team should be very careful when determining this response, particularly in spinal injuries. The health care provider takes into the notice of any muscle relaxants or sedative agents before concluding that there is no motor response (Agrawal, 2018).

Literature Review

The GCS is a simple and consistent measure of the level of consciousness. This scale went on to be known and used by most of the neurosurgical units worldwide. The Institute of Neurological sciences Glasgow is a world leader in brain injury research and clinical care (Agrawal, 2018). A study conducted to assess the Neurological assessment of patients with brain stroke and eye-opening without any external stimulus in emergency and intensive care units. The results show that the neurological assessment of patients with brain stroke with the GCS scale is average (Kimboka, 2017). Study results show that the verbal stimulus loud sound is needed in patients with serious neurological injuries to assess the GCS scale that makes the patient open the eyes. About 78% of the health care team agreed and satisfied with verbal stimulus. 32% of them do not agree/disagree about the GCS scale findings. The verbal stimulus is not a grasp to open eyes. The study results also retrieved that the sound should be sufficiently loud to provoke a response of a patient with brain trauma (Mushtaq et al., 2017). Study results show that nurses not have marked knowledge regarding research because of not having provision, knowledge, and environment. The same is the case with the approach of the nurses concerning research. The attitude of the nurses is not encouraging to research due to the absence of awareness, understanding environment, and capacity. Consequently, the health care management should emphasize on the improvement of awareness and attitude of the nurses regarding research (Quraeshi et al., 2018). A study results show that if the patients' talking in a random way or which having no conversational exchange and showing Incomprehensible noises like moaning, groaning speech these all indicates a high degree of dis-functioning in the nervous system. The results also indicated that motor responses which are the obeying commands in the Glasgow coma scale rule out grasp reflex or postural adjustment. The patients with the neuronal dis-functions most likely to show no motor response (Teasdale and Iverson, 2019). The study results show that significant differences exist between assessments of the Glasgow coma scale. The GCS motor score is standardly used to measure neurological status in patients with head injuries. It is measured at different time points after injury in patients with traumatic brain injuries. A study found

that the arrangement between the prehospital and emergency department. The GCS motor scores were highest for minor and severe scores on the 1 to 6 scale. The effect of the GCS motor score is more important as assessed in the field and compared to the admission assessment in the systematic analysis. The differences were smaller after correction. The effect of pupillary reactivity was similar at both assessments in all situations (Majdan et al., 2015).

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A Cross-sectional observational study design utilized to achieve the aim of the current study Nurses knowledge and practice regarding GCS techniques implementation.

Sitting

The present study conducted at the ICUs and emergency department of a tertiary care hospital of Lahore.

Target population

The target population of the study was Registered nurses who are working in the emergency department and Intensive Care Units.

Study duration

This study took 4 months, from February 28.2020 to May 3, 2020.

Sample size

Slovin's sampling formula used to find the sample size of the study population. $n = 150$.

Sampling technique

Convenient sampling technique used to collect data from the participant.

Procedure Sampling

A convenience sampling method was used from which participants were recruited and a questioner was given to fill. The researcher approached each of the nurses available during the time of data collection. The nurses who wished to participate would read and sign a consent form.

RESULTS

This study was conducted over 150 participants. The demographic variable revealed that 58 (38.7%) of the participant were with the age group of 20-25 years, 26-30 years of age were 53 (35.3%), 35 (23.3%) of the population having age group of 31-35 years and more than 36 years were only 4 (2.7%). According to sex differences, 19 (12.7%) of the population consisted of male and 131 (87.3%) was female. Based on their qualification, 100 (60%) were diploma holders and 50 (40%) were with the bachelor's degree. Experience of the 67 (44.7) participants in emergency and ICU departments was 1-6 years. 79 (52.7%) were having 7-14 years of experience and 4 (2.7%) participants having experience of 15 years and above. Table 1

Knowledge

In response to the question "have you ever cared for a patient with altered level of consciousness who required assessment of GCS" out of 150 (100%) participants? 75 (50%) answered Yes and 75 (50%) replied No. In the questionnaire, 2nd question, have you had any recent training about GCS? 70 participants (46.7%) marked Yes and 80 participants (53.3%) chose option no. While answering the following question, "What is the function of GCS out of 150(100%) participants? 44 (29.3%) responded right and, 106 (70.7%) replied wrong. The question has been asked for eye-opening, 44 (29.3%) respond to pupil reaction and best motor response, 49 (32.7%) best verbal response and motor deficit, and 50 (33.3%) best verbal response and best motor response. In question 05, the participants asked for the best score for the GCS scale out of 100% (150 Participants) 51 (34.0%) answered right and 99(66.0%) answered wrong. In response to the question, the worse score for the scale 24 (16.0%) of the participants marked 4, 78 (52.0%) respond right, 82 (48.0%) chose the wrong answer. In question 07 the respondent has been asked for "GCS score that indicates a critical situation, the examiner should be alert to be" 32 (21.3%) respond right and remaining 118 (79%) answered wrong. This is alarming about the lack of GCS knowledge among nurses. The results that indicate a moderate head injury are between: out of (150) 100% participants 61 (40.7%) selected, 12-9 which is a right answer and the remaining 89 (59.3%) selected wrong answers. In answer to a question during the use of GCS, the most adequate response for the score is 61(40.7%). This shows the poor knowledge level for GCS monitoring among nurses. For the question to assess the best verbal response, the examiner should begin with question. Out of 100% of participants answered as following, 55 (36.7%) selected the option "asking simple questions about location, time and self which is the right option, and the remaining 95 (63.3%)

Table 1. Section B: Knowledge about the Glasgow Coma Scale

S#	Question	Response	Frequency %
1	Have you ever cared for a patient with an altered level of consciousness who required assessment of GCS?	Yes	75(50.0)
		No	75(50.0)
2	Have you had any recent training about GCS?	Yes	70(46.7)
		No	80(53.3)
3	What is the function of GCS?	(a) Evaluate the level of consciousness	44(29.3)
		(b) Evaluate cognitive changes	90(60.0)
		(c) Evaluate the cognitive level of knowledge	16(10.7)
4	Three components of GCS are:	(a) Eye-opening, pupil reaction, and best motor response	51(34.0)
		(b) Eye-opening, best verbal response, and motor deficit	49(32.7)
		(c) Eye-opening, best verbal response, and best motor response	50(33.3)
5	Best score for the scale is	(a) 15	51(34.0)
		(b) 13	77(51.3)
		(c) 8	22(14.7)
		(d) 5	0(0.0)
6	Worse score for the scale is:	(a) 4	24(16.0)
		(b) 3	78(52.0)
		(c) 1	24(16.0)
		(d) 0	24(16.0)
7	A GCS score that indicates a critical situation the examiner should be alert to be	(a) GCS \leq 15	55(36.7)
		(b) GCS \leq 8	63(42.0)
		(c) GCS \leq 7	32(21.3)
		(d) GCS \leq 5	0(0.0)
8	When documenting GCS, the following criteria should be mentioned (select all which is applicable):	(a) Presence of endotracheal intubation and eyelid edema	52(34.7)
		(b) Respiratory and hemodynamic stability	47(31.3)
		(c) Use of sedatives and neuromuscular blockage	51(34.0)
9	GCS results can be divided into three categories – mild, moderate, and severe. The results that indicate a moderate head injury is between:	(a) 8-3	16(10.7)
		(b) 15-13	73(48.7)
		(c) 12-9	61(40.7)
		(d) 14-8	0(0.0)
10	During the use of GCS, the most adequate response for the score is	(a) The first response presented by the patient	37(24.7)
		(b) The best response presented by the patient	61(40.7)
		(c) The last response presented by the patient	52(34.7)

Table 1. Continue

11	To assess eye-opening, the examiner should begin with:	(a) Verbally requesting the patient to open his/her eyes	45(30.0)
		(b) Calling the patient's name out loud	69(46.0)
		(c) Using painful stimuli	36(24.0)
		(d) Standing next to the patient's bed	
12	To assess the best verbal response, the examiner should begin with	(a) Making different questions	60(40.0)
		(b) Asking simple questions about location, time, and self.	55(36.7)
		(c) Asking the patient about pain location	36(23.3)
13	To assess the best motor response, the examiner should begin with	(a) A verbal command requesting a motor response	24(16.0)
		(b) The use of pain full stimulus	61(40.)
		(c) Observing muscle strength	59(39.3)
		(d) Observing the range movement	6(4.0)
14	In GCS it is important to document	(a) Only the total score	55(36.7)
		(b) Describing responses obtained	63(42.0)
		(c) Scoring each indicator	32(21.3)
		(d) Scoring each indicator, total score, and describe when necessary	0(0.0)

participants selected wrong answers. In response to the question to assess the best motor response, the examiner should begin with; participants selected the answer as following, 24(16.0%) chose a verbal command requesting a motor response, which is the right answer. Remaining 126 (84%) participants marked the wrong answer. For the last question of knowledge related to GCS "In GCS it is important to document" all 100% participants marked the wrong answer which is again showing the lack of knowledge. In the conclusion of knowledge section, according to the above-mentioned questions of knowledge assessment regarding GCS implementation techniques, notified that 34.3% of the total population knows well about GCS implementation techniques and 65.7% of the population did not know about GCS implementation techniques, in other words almost 51 participants had good knowledge of GCS implementation techniques in ICU and Emergency setting, almost 99 participants out of 150 have poor or bad knowledge regarding GCS implementation techniques. Table 2

In this portion of the results, the skills performance of each individual. The checklist consists of three portions. Firstly, observed for "Eye-opening response", which consists of further four options for GCS evaluation. Every individual has observed for each score of the checklist. Their right performance has been nominated with "Yes", and those performed on the wrong way or miss the option has been presented with "No".

Section 1 (Eye-opening)

All the mentioned questions asked and the observation details showed that 49.16% of the population performed this section in the right way, while the remaining 50.84% of the population missed the options and perform wrongly.

Section 2 (Verbal response)

All the stated questions enquired and the observation

Table 2. Observational Checklist for Nurses Practice on GCS

S#	Skills to be Observed	Step	Response	Frequency %
	Eye open			
	Observe if the patient opens eyes spontaneously	4	Yes No	67(44.7) 83(55.3)
	Calls and commands patient and observe if patients open the eyes	3	Yes No	83(55.3) 67(44.7)
	Causes pain to the patient to see if eyes open with a painful stimulus	2	Yes No	80(53.3) 70(46.7)
	Acknowledges if no eye-opening even after application of all previously described stimuli	1	Yes No	65(43.3) 85(56.7)
	Verbal response			
	Asks the patient to assess orientation to time, space and aware of the self	5	Yes No	105(70.0) 45(30.0)
	Able to test whether a patient can answer questions, but incorrectly, as they are disoriented and confused	4	Yes No	66(44.0) 84(56.0)
	Identify inappropriate responses from patients	3	Yes No	64(42.7) 86(57.3)
	Able to detect incomprehensible speech from patients	2	Yes No	105(70.0) 45(30.0)
	Observe if there is no verbalization of any type	1	Yes No	77(51.3) 73(48.7)
	Motor response			
	Observes if patient obeys a command for movement	6	Yes No	68(45.3) 82(54.7)
	Observes if there is localization in response to pain stimulus	5	Yes No	84(56.0) 66(44.0)
	Observe if the patient can withdraw from pain	4	Yes No	59(39.3) 91(60.7)
	Observe abnormal movement (spastic)flexion, decorticate posture	3	Yes No	77(51.7) 73(48.7)
	Detection of extensor (rigid) response, decelerate posture	2	Yes No	69(46.0) 81(54.0)
	Identify if no response even after the application of all previously described stimuli.	1	Yes No	90(60.0) 60(40.0)

details showed that 55.6 % of the participant done this section with the right technique, while the remaining 44.4% of participant missed the option and perform wrongly

Section 3 (Motor response)

Entire revealed questions asked, observation details showed that 49.6 % of the participant performed this section in the right way, while the remaining 50.4 of the participants neglected the option and performed wrongly

DISCUSSION

According to this study, a lot of participants did not have sufficient knowledge of GCS implementation techniques in the ICU and emergency departments. According to facts and figures, only 34.3% of Nurses have sufficient knowledge GCS implementation techniques, on the other

hands, 65.7% of the population did not know about GCS implementation techniques, in other words almost 51 participants had good knowledge and almost 99 participants out of 150 have poor or bad knowledge regarding GCS implementation techniques. The same responses were also identified in the results of research done by ThiHien and Chae (2011), were concluded that the nurses were lacking the necessary knowledge about GCS especially when it comes to the clinical setting, however, very few nurses (13.3%) indicated that their current knowledge on the application of GCS is adequate. This percentage is lower than that reported in Nigeria by Anarado and colleagues (2016) in a similar study where 41.7% of nurses reported to have a good level of knowledge of the GCS. This study consists of another part, in which the assessed knowledge proved with the help of practical performance or skills implementation. All the participants were observed for the implementation of GCS techniques. Their practices and scoring figures presented, that they don't have sufficient skills to assess the eye-opening, verbal, and motor

responses of the patients in a particular way and giving a proper score to taken Responses. The figures showed that they have good knowledge or GCS implementation skills but this not enough for GCS accuracy. A similar study conducted by Kimboka (2017), and postulated that there was less understanding of the neurological bases, and clinical application of the GCS, with a lack of continuing educational updates on the GCS. This ultimately hinders the proper application of the GCS during the assessment of critically ill patients. In addition to that, nurses in this study who had a higher level of education had less work experience (60.2%) and as the level of education increased there was a better performance on the GCS assessment. This indicates that the higher the level of education ensures the higher level of competence in the application of procedures including GCS assessment.

CONCLUSION

The best and common system to measure the level of consciousness is the Glasgow coma scale (GCS). Nurses have a low level of knowledge about GCS assessment. The majority of nurses did not know the best score of GCS. There was a large discrepancy between the knowledge score and nurse's "perception of their current knowledge. There was less understanding of the neurological bases and clinical application of the GCS, with a lack of continuing educational updates on the GCS. These factors, together with inadequate knowledge will limit their capacity for assessment, clinical judgment, and decision making in managing unconscious or deteriorating patients.

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